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Agriculture waste pyrolysis and thermocomposting for renewable energy in sustainable agri-food sector

D1.2 Ethics Plan

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

1. Introduction

TEAPOTS is a European project that aims at creating value from waste biomass to induce the diffusion of the correct disposal of agricultural waste while promoting the use of plant enhancers and soil conditioners to promote soil biodiversity. The project will experiment to prove the benefit of a local network of biomass producers with a centralised prosumer of renewable energy.

In return, it will give back high value ready-to-use plant enhancers and soil improvers to increase fields' productivity and soil biodiversity. In other words, TEAPOTS aims at the extraction of value from biomass through the production of:

- 1 renewable energy able to continuously meet end-users' energy demand;
- 2 new exploitable products (i.e., plant enhancer compost and biochar as soil amendments).

The involvement of several actors requires a particular effort in assuring the respect of the use of their information and the fair involvement during the project.

2. TEAPOTS activities including human participants

2.1 Human participants definition

According to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA¹), all subjects involved in the research, whether human, animal, or non-living, should be treated with respect and care. The health, safety or welfare of a community or collaborators should not be compromised. Researchers should be sensitive to their research subjects. Protocols governing research involving human subjects must not be violated. Research with human participants should guarantee principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice.

TEAPOTS takes a comprehensive approach to human involvement in research. For the sake of the current deliverable, human participants are people involved in TEAPOTS' activities (research activities, events, workshops etc...) without being part of the project team.

If partner staff is employed on the project, and they will be using technologies developed in the project itself, and their time is billed to the project, then they are not research participants unless they are performing activities outside of their contract of employment. For instance, if the research activity is about the impact of the technology use on humans, in that case they can be considered as human participants. Third party entities which provide a service to the project are also excluded. Conversely, if an activity involves a person outside the project team (e.g., someone who participates in a survey), then it should be considered a human participant. We should apply the same reasoning if the research activity can affect a person or pose a risk of harm, risk, or impact on their dignity. In case of uncertainty, it is our standard practice to assume that person

¹ <https://allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/European-Code-of-Conduct-Revised-Edition-2023.pdf>

as a human participant. This approach enables us to identify and mitigate potential risks by implementing appropriate protective measures.

2.2 Activities involving human participants

In some of the TEAPOTS activities we are seeking the perspective of organisations on the TEAPOTS technologies and activities. In this framework, people who completed the surveys are requested to participate as a representative of their organisation. The physical presence and interaction of people attending TEAPOTS workshops implies that they will be considered as human participants even if they represent an organisation.

Task	Lead partner	Human participants involvement
6.2	AUA	Surveys administered to gather info on the final inputs from the end users. Surveys will be anonymised, personal data will be acquired only after written consent in order to reach participants with communications for follow-ups and events participation or co-creation. Data will be used to better understand the potential difficulties in the adoption of TEAPOTS' solutions.
7.1	AUA	Surveys to determine end-users' needs at the starting point of the project to help the initial development of the technology. Surveys will be anonymised, personal data will be acquired only after written consent in order to reach participants with communications for follow-ups and events participation or co-creation. Data will be used to better understand the potential difficulties in the adoption of TEAPOTS' solutions. Furthermore, information will be employed to direct the further development of technologies and to identify potential markets and clients.
7.2	FENIX	Dissemination activities will require the involvement of people in dedicated events, organised by project partners or through participation to fairs, events, workshops, webinars and more organised by other entities. Personal information will be acquired through the described channels (section 3) to ensure the diffusion of TEAPOTS' innovations and approaches in both general and expert public. Photos, registrations and other kind of personal data will be used to promote TEAPOTS activities.
7.3	ERSAF	Dissemination and Communication activities dedicated to local associations and public bodies. The aim of the acquired information is to evaluate policy constraints, the presence of public and private investments, the availability of public procurement pull for new solutions. Data acquired will help in the definition of policy recommendations through the involvement of experts in dedicated discussions.

TABLE 1 HUMAN PARTICIPANTS INVOLVEMENT IN TEAPOTS

2.3 Benefits

Several activities provide direct benefits to the participants since they will receive free training on the project's technologies and innovations. Furthermore, TEAPOTS partners will organise events and workshops to offer opportunities for collaboration with other organisations. The main benefit from this kind of activities is the creation of a wide European network to promote collaboration within diverse experts and members of the society.

3. Recruitment criteria

3.1 Recruitment

The criteria for recruiting human participants are derived from the purpose and design of the research activity. General human **participants profiles** have been developed by TEAPOTS in its research activities, including specific criteria for each individual activity.

- **Knowledge and proficiency.** In general, TEAPOTS looks for human participants with expertise or experience in the areas the project is working on (for example, companies in the power production value chain, potential end-users of project technologies). Expertise is broadly defined, to include people with practical, day-to-day experience. Thus, human participants with no expertise or experience in the project context will not be considered.
- **Benefit from Training.** Some of TEAPOTS's work with human participants includes training activities and workshops. Given the budget constraints and the use of public funds, it is important to select candidates who possess the necessary skills to benefit from the training and who can apply it effectively in their activities.
- **Volunteers only.** TEAPOTS partners will only recruit volunteer participants that will not be coerced, or pressured, in any way into participating. If partners believe a participant has been coerced or pressured, they will be removed from the research activity. Asymmetric power relationships can sometimes invalidate the voluntariness of consent; none of the participants will be in a situation of subordination to the researchers. TEAPOTS will not use manipulation or deception as part of its research activities, nor will participants be induced through payment or otherwise to participate (reasonable expenses may be covered for participants). All participants will be unpaid volunteers and will be free to leave the research activity at any time without any negative consequence. As part of the involvement in the project activities, all participants will be made aware of the possibility to withdraw from participation freely at any time.
- **No vulnerable people.** TEAPOTS partners will only recruit adults with sufficient mental capacity to consent. No research activity in TEAPOTS will require the participation of children, vulnerable individuals, or persons with limited intellectual ability. If TEAPOTS partners consider any individual to lack the necessary competence, they will not be involved in the research activity.

- **Diversity and inclusion.** TEAPOTS is committed to diversity and inclusion to promote the high quality of its results. TEAPOTS Consortium will take additional measures where necessary (for example, additional advertising and recruitment) to try to reach the most representative pool of human participants.
- **Age inclusion.** The outcomes of TEAPOTS are intended to benefit individuals of all age groups (in accordance with legal working age requirements). Therefore, our activities aim to engage a broad spectrum of ages, ensuring representation across various employment and educational contexts.

Clear criteria should be established for including and excluding research participants according to the TEAPOTS research design, as well as to provide a justification for including a data subject in the research.

Different recruitment channels will be used to identify and select research participants. The methods described below will help to contact them and seek for their participation or elicit their support in helping the consortium to gain access to the needed research data and/or subjects. The content in each of these methods should be consistent without significant variations.

Generally, a combination of the following ones is used:

- Phone calls (e.g., asking to relevant stakeholder organisations to suggest potential participants).
- E-mails.
- Project industry advisory board and stakeholders who have signed a letter of interest for the project. The project will include a group of organisations with an interest in the project and which would be willing to co-operate (e.g., providing representatives to participate in some activities) because, want to learn more about the project.
- Social media to promote voluntary public participation in the research (e.g., X, Facebook, LinkedIn).
- Face-to-face meetings (during events where TEAPOTS will participate as organizer or as a guest).
- Internet/database search (e.g., finding contact details for suitable participants on their organisational websites).
- Online interviews (e.g. Zoom, Microsoft Teams).
- Online surveys (to identify individuals who meet the specific research criteria.).

3.2 Ethical risks

Partners do not foresee any significant risks for the participants in this research. The health and safety measures partners have in place of researchers can be extended to support research participants.

4. Informed consent and informed consent procedures

It is widely agreed that informed consent is the first principle in research activities involving human beings. This guarantees that participants exercise their autonomy and dignity, and for a researcher to enable this

through respecting them as persons. In research ethics, consent is considered valid only if people meet the following requirements:

- 1) They have adequate information about what they are being asked to consent to;
- 2) They can voluntarily consent to it;
- 3) They have the capacity to understand what their consent means.

Disrespecting a person's consent implies the violation of these three principles (one or more). TEAPOTS partners acknowledge and accept that consent will only be considered valid when all three conditions are met.

Partners will provide comprehensive information (in a clear and concise language and translated when necessary) on the activities that participants are being asked to do, and what will happen to their data. Participants will be able to take time to consider the meaning of the information they are given before signing an informed consent form. Retaining an informed consent form for each human participants allows us to properly record and demonstrate that consent, if necessary. TEAPOTS' human participant recruitment criteria (e.g., no children, vulnerable people, no coercion, etc.) aim to ensure that participants can give consent in a free and informed manner.

Withdrawal of consent: the consortium will ensure that research participants can withdraw their consent freely at any time. Thus, it should be clear about how and when any research participant could withdraw their consent to participate in the research.

Participants will always receive (regardless of the type of activity) a detailed information sheet and will be asked to sign an informed consent form (European Commission, 2021) (these may be combined into a single document for convenience).

The information sheet will inform them about:

- The purposes of the research and how the results of the research will be used.
- A comprehensive description of the procedures implemented to protect the privacy: the levels of confidentiality, the measures to protect the data, the duration of the data storage and how they will be managed at the end of the research.
- The experimental procedures and a detailed description of the participants involvement, including the expected duration and all the relevant procedures.
- Anticipated risks or discomforts that can reasonably be expected to affect the research subjects during and following their participation.
- Any benefits expected to arise for the participants or others involved.
- Procedures in case of incidental findings.

- Researchers contacts: they can be contacted at any time to answer pertinent questions (e.g., research, participant's rights) and in the case of a research- related injury.
- A clear statement about the voluntary nature of participation. The refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which the participant would otherwise be entitled. Additionally, the participant retains the right to withdraw from participation at any time without facing any consequence or repercussion.
- Information about the project organisation and funding.

The informed consent form provided aims to record two main requirements:

1. The individual's informed consent to participate in the research;
2. The individual's consent for the processing of personal data necessary for the research activity in compliance with data protection law.

The informed consent form will be made available in relevant languages; both physical and digital signatures are accepted. Regardless the means of collection of the informed consent, a full copy of the latter will be given to participants to keep. The TEAPOTS consortium will secure informed consent from all stakeholders participating interviews or any such engagements with research subjects **before the commencement of any data collection**. Moreover, research subjects will be informed beforehand about their possibility to withdraw from the research or interview at any time, without the need for explanation.

Templates for the information sheet and informed consent forms that will be used within the project are provided as section 5 of this report.

4.1 Data protection and GDPR compliance

The notion of “consent” in human subject research ethics and data protection are not the same, but similar. Within the context of data protection, “consent” represents one of multiple permissible legal bases for processing personal data. The point at which consent is sought for participation in research is an appropriate point to also ask for consent for the processing of personal data necessary for that research activity. Therefore, we also use the information sheet to meet the requirements of article 13 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regarding the data subject transparency. TEAPOTS information sheets are written to inform people in clear and simple language about:

- The existence of the data subject's rights and how they can be exercised or claimed.
- The main elements of the processing operation (i.e., types of personal data, legal basis, the purposes, data retention period and any eventual data transfers).
- The contact details of the parties involved (e.g., data controllers, DPO and further recipients of that data, if present)

- Since our legal basis for the personal data elaboration (related to the activities with human participants) is the consent of the data subject, the consent form also allows the opportunity to seek this consent. The GDPR places several requirements upon consent.

Legal GDPR consent must be:

- **Specific** – Consent will be asked for each purpose of data processing (e.g., if we want to process personal data for research but also for dissemination activities, we should ask separately for both);
- **Informed** – Data subjects must understand what they are consenting to. This implies they need at least the information above together with the information about the possibility of withdrawing their consent;
- **Unambiguous** – It must be clear that the data subject has consented in a way that can be distinguished from non-consent. For example, continuing to browse a web page, does not entail consent for data processing. A lack of objection to a statement of data processing does not entail proactive unambiguous consent;
- **Freely given** – Is not coerced or obtained with deception. It can be withdrawn at any time by the data subjects, without any detriment to them.

For these reasons, our consent forms include both requests for consent to participate in the research activity and separately, consent for the processing of personal data in relation to that activity. Further details about the TEAPOTS approach to the protection of personal data are provided in the forthcoming D1.3 Data Management Plan (DMP).

4.2 Recording informed consent

It is important to keep records of consent for the research participation to protect the research subject, the researchers, and to allow problem solving. The partner organisation responsible for administering the research activity in question will retain the consent forms on file. The latter do not need to be shared and should not be uploaded to the project's shared cloud storage. The processing of consent forms is included in the DMP. Consent forms should be kept separately from the data processed. Completed informed consent forms will include personal data, thus their sharing should be only when strictly necessary for the research activity. Completed informed consent forms should be kept on file, securely, by the partner responsible of their collection, unless there is an evidenced need to share them with other partners or with the EC.

4.3 Specific informed consent requirements for TEAPOTS activities

In addition to the already described general requirements, different TEAPOTS research activities have specific requirements for informed consent.

4.3.1 Survey

- **Separated personal data and research consent:** The survey can be completed anonymously, i.e. no consent is required for the processing of personal data. Participants can also decide to share their contact (e.g., email address) at the end of the survey, giving their consent to receive communications about further project results and activities. The necessary GDPR information and consent request are presented at the point this information is requested, rather than with the research ethics information at the start of the survey.
- **Open research data consent:** To make research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable, it may be useful to make the data set produced freely accessible for re-use by other researchers. At this stage, asking for participant consent for this simplifies this process.
- **Sharing for translation purposes:** Responses need to be translated into a shared language for analysis. This may involve sharing these responses with other partners.

4.3.2 Workshops and training activities

- **Video recordings and photos sharing** – sharing of communication materials is necessary to allow dissemination and exploitation activities. The consent form for these events therefore needs to request the data subject's consent for this use.
- **Physical training activities - Health and safety considerations.** The content of these training activities will be determined later in the project. If any of these contain physical components, the information sheet should include a brief description of any associated risks.

4.3.3 Stakeholders contact/interview

- No additional specific requirements

5. Templates of informed consent and information sheets

Template information and informed consent sheets for different types of human participant research are listed below (survey, interviews, workshops & training). These documents must be supplied to research participants in languages that they can understand. Translated copies of these sheets must be retained on record by the project.

5.1 Consent form - general

**info partner researcher(s), responsible for the area:
(name)**

Address for correspondence:

Email: ... Telephone: ...

Date

Dear

You are invited to participate in this project, and we are required to provide a participant information sheet and consent form to inform you about the study, to convey that participation is voluntary, to explain the potential risks and benefits of participation, and to empower you to make an informed decision. You should feel free to ask us any questions you may have. If you agree to take part, we will ask you to sign a consent form. Please take as much time as you need to read it. You should only consent to take part in this study when you feel that you understand what is being asked of you and you have had enough time to think about your decision.

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

We are undertaking this research at (**partner institution**) as the organization representing (**country**) in the larger European Horizon Europe project TEAPOTS that brings together a wide range of actors across Europe. You have been contacted about this study because you are a farmer/forester/industry producing agricultural waste that may entail costs or risks and you are looking for ways to dispose or utilise it. Your answers will form part of our study on ways to utilise waste throughout Europe.

TEAPOTS

TEAPOTS is a European project that aims at creating value from waste biomass to induce the diffusion of the correct disposal of agricultural waste while promoting the use of plant enhancers and soil conditioners to promote soil biodiversity. The project will experiment to prove the benefit of a local network of biomass producers with a centralised prosumer of renewable energy. In return, it will give back high value ready-to-use plant enhancers and soil improvers to increase fields' productivity and soil biodiversity. In other words, TEAPOTS aims at the extraction of value from biomass through the production of i) renewable energy able to continuously meet end-users' energy demand, and ii) new exploitable products (i.e., plant enhancer compost and biochar as soil amendments).

Why are my details important?

The more participants included in this survey the more beneficial it will be to both the agricultural sector and to relevant industries and research institutes. Your contribution is very important in increasing the understanding of farmers' needs and interests and identifying factors influencing waste management.

WHAT YOU WILL DO

Your participation is entirely voluntary. If you consent to take part, you will be asked to answer to a number of questions included in the TEAPOTS questionnaire. This questionnaire will take you around x minutes to complete. All information provided in the interview and surveys will be kept anonymous and strict confidentiality will be ensured.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS

The findings of this study will be presented in (country) and in Europe. As aforementioned, it is the aim of this research to promote solutions regarding effective waste management, while capturing stakeholders' needs and innovative ideas.

POTENTIAL RISKS

We do not foresee any negative effects arising from your participation in this study. Please understand that you are free to withdraw from participation in advance of the interview as well as to stop the interview at any stage. All information and topics discussed are confidential and the content of the discussion/questionnaire data will not be disclosed to third parties.

PRIVACY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

We will collect your name, organisation, and professional email address if further details are necessary when analyzing the data. However, your participation in this survey will be treated anonymously and your personal data will only be kept for internal research purposes; your data and that of other persons and places mentioned in the survey and/or interview will remain confidential at all times.

In case the survey and/or interview is recorded, all electronic and recorded versions of the survey interview will be securely stored and treated anonymously. The only record of your participation in the interview will be stored in (researcher location) in a secure location for the duration of the study in case we need to contact you again. Anonymised versions of the interview data will be shared with and analyzed by TEAPOTS project partners.

The results of this study will be published or presented at professional meetings, but the material used will not at any time allow the identification of any of the participants in this survey.

YOUR RIGHTS TO PARTICIPATE, SAY NO, OR REQUEST MY WITHDRAWAL

Participation in this research project is completely voluntary. You have the right to say no. You may change your mind at any time or withdraw. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

CONTACT INFORMATION FOR QUESTIONS AND CONCERNS

If you have any questions about this study, or about your role or rights as a research participant, please contact the researchers and their Data Protection Officer (DPO) at the address above.

(researcher) + (contact of the DPO of the partner's organization)

Summary

Participation in this study is based on the clear understanding that your participation is voluntary and can be withdrawn at any time. A consent form accompanies this participant information sheet. A copy of both will be provided to you. You are required to sign a copy of the consent form should you agree to participate in this study - please return one copy of the signed consent form. Thank you for considering taking part in this study.

5.2 Informed consent form for surveys and events

TEAPOTS (agriculTurE wAste PyrOlysis and Thermocomposting for renewable energy in Sustainable agri-food sector)

**info partner researcher(s), responsible for the area:
(name)**

Address for correspondence:

Email: ... Telephone: ...

Date

Please tick the boxes

1. I confirm that I have read the participation information sheet dated **(Date)** for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions
2. I confirm that I understand the information provided and have had enough time to consider the information.
3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time.
4. In signing this consent form I [Participant] agree to volunteer to participate in this research study being conducted by **(leading partner researcher)** and research colleagues.
5. I agree:
 - to the data being audio-recorded for the purposes of data processing
- and,
 - to the interview being archived in a digital repository subject to my name and identifying information being removed
6. I understand that I will participate in a recorded interview with the researcher on the agreed topic.

7. I grant full authorization for the use of the above information on the full understanding that my participation will be kept anonymous and confidentiality will be preserved in public use of these data.
8. I understand that participation is completely voluntary and that I am free to withdraw my data at any time, without giving a reason.

Participant

Date

Signature

Researcher

Date

Signature

